

Exploring the Dispersive and Saline Soil of Anambra State, Nigeria - A Focus on Tunnel Erosion Prone Areas

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Abstract

Tunnel erosion, like other forms of erosion, is caused by dispersive soils and to determine the extent of soil dispersion in a particular area, various indices such as Exchangeable Sodium Percentage (ESP), Sodium Absorption Ratio (SAR), Dispersive Ratio (DR), and Clay Dispersive Ratio (CDR) are usually analysed. This research will focus on assessing the extent of soil dispersion in areas affected by tunnel erosion, specifically near a sinkhole. Three sinkhole sites were selected for examination: Awka site 1, Awka site 2, and Agulu. A total of 24 soil samples were collected and analyzed, with 15 samples obtained from the immediate vicinity of the sinkholes and 9 samples from locations at least 2 kilometers away. The study investigated parameters such as Magnesium (Mg) levels, Sodium (Na) levels, Calcium (Ca) levels, Effective Cation Exchange Capacity (ECEC), soil texture, Erodibility Factor (EF), Water Dispersible Clay (WDC), Water Dispersible Silt (WDS), Dispersive Ratio (DR), Clay Dispersive Ratio (CDR), Sodium Absorption Ratio (SAR), and Exchangeable Sodium Percentage (ESP). The results indicate that the study areas have a higher proportion of sandy soil and a lower proportion of clay and silt soils compared to typical soil compositions. The water dispersible indices range from low to moderate, with the low clay and silt content contributing to the overall low water dispersible properties of the soil. Most of the ESP values exceed the threshold of 15%, particularly in areas further away from the sinkhole site, indicating high soil salinity and a positive relationship with sodicity. DR and CDR values range from moderate to high, suggesting that the soils are easily dispersive and prone to erosion. The combination of high ESP values and high DR and CDR percentages increases the likelihood of soil degradation, reduced water infiltration, and potential loss of topsoil, that leads to soil erosion.

Keywords: Tunnel erosion, soil dispersion, saline soil, exchangeable sodium percentage, Sodium absorption ratio, dispersive ratio DR, and clay dispersive ratio, Anambra state

Introduction

Tunnel erosion refers to the progressive displacement of soil particles by water, ultimately resulting in the formation of subsurface soil channels or pipes. This phenomenon is highly destructive and can be observed across diverse landscapes, including agricultural fields, forests, and urban areas[1]–[3]. Notably, tunnel erosion is not limited to specific climatic or geological settings. Instead, it has been documented in various environmental conditions[4]. The consequences of tunnel erosion are far-reaching and can give rise to a range of environmental problems. Soil infertility, loss of crop productivity, and water pollution are among the significant issues associated with this erosive process.

The subterranean world forged by tunnel erosion unveils a captivating phenomenon that often eludes casual observation[5]. It is within this hidden landscape that intricate networks of tunnels are meticulously carved out by the relentless hydraulic force of water acting upon the soil. As water continues to flow through the permeable layer beneath the soil surface, it exerts pressure on the surrounding particles that gradually erode the soil and create pathways for its escape[6]. Over time, these pathways have the potential to expand and deepen, giving rise to tunnels that span considerable distances, traversing beneath fields, roads, and even built infrastructure. The evolution of these tunnels is a testament to the dynamic nature of tunnel erosion, as it delicately shapes the subterranean environment.

The ramifications of tunnel erosion extend far beyond its immediate impact, presenting substantial challenges for landowners, infrastructure developers, and environmentalists alike[4]. The stability of the land situated above these concealed tunnels is compromised, resulting in the emergence of sinkholes, landslides, and structural damages that demand attention and mitigation[5], [7].

For landowners, the consequences of tunnel erosion can be particularly worrisome, as it jeopardizes the integrity of their properties and poses a threat to the safety of inhabitants. Likewise, infrastructure developers must grapple with the implications of tunnel erosion, as it presents a considerable risk to the stability of roads, buildings, and other vital structures. Furthermore, environmentalists are confronted with the task of safeguarding the delicate ecological balance disrupted by tunnel erosion, recognizing the potential for habitat degradation and the detrimental effects on flora and fauna.

The complex phenomenon of tunnel erosion is primarily instigated by the runoff of water resulting from excessive rainfall or irrigation events when the soil's capacity to absorb water is surpassed[8]. Researchers have recognized that numerous factors contribute to the soil's inability to effectively retain water, with land-use practices, climate conditions, slope characteristics, soil compaction, and composition emerging as prominent influencers[5], [8]–[10].

Land-use practices, such as deforestation and urbanization, can significantly exacerbate the risk of tunnel erosion by diminishing vegetation cover and augmenting the proportion of impervious surfaces[11], [12]. Consequently, the reduced presence of vegetation impedes water absorption, while the increased prevalence of impermeable surfaces amplifies surface runoff, intensifying the erosive forces at play. Moreover, soils characterized by inadequate physical and chemical properties are more susceptible to tunnel erosion[13]. One such example is sodicity, a chemical process that transpires when the soil exhibits a relatively high sodium content[13]. This leads to the swelling, sealing, and dispersion of the soil's clay particles[14]–[16]. As the soil disperses, its capacity to absorb water diminishes, resulting in the excess unabsorbed water cascading over the surface, progressively scouring its pathway and eventually creating tunnels[17].

In order to assess the extent of soil dispersion occurring in a specific soil, numerous indices are utilized, including Exchangeable Sodium Percentage (ESP)[17], Sodium Absorption Ratio (SAR)[18], Dispersive Ratio (DR)[19], and Clay Dispersive Ratio (CR)[16]. Numerous literatures have shown the value of these indices in quantifying the degree of dispersion within a given soil[13], [16], [17], [19], [20]. Consequently, our research endeavors focus on the comprehensive analysis of ESP, SAR, DR, and CR within the soil surrounding a sinkhole. By conducting a rigorous examination of these indices, we aim to gain a deeper understanding of the ongoing soil dispersion processes in the vicinity of the sinkhole.

Study Area

Figure 1. The study area with an insert of Anambra state and Nigeria (PA = Piping Area, NPA = Non-piping area)

In this study, our focus encompasses on two distinct sites in the Awka South area and one site in the Aniocha Local Government area both in Anambra state (as shown in Figure 1). The first site, referred to as Awka Site 1, is strategically positioned at coordinates (6.2232°N and 7.0824°E). At this location, we have identified a soil pipe that spans approximately 5cm in diameter. The impact of this pipe on a constructed road has resulted in significant damage, manifesting in the creation of two sinkholes, each boasting a diameter of approximately 70cm (as illustrated in Figure 2a).

Moving on to Awka Site 2, which can be found at coordinates (6.222°N and 7.0819°E), we have discovered a soil pipe that has been in existence for roughly three years. This particular pipe has given rise to a series of holes, each averaging 10cm in diameter. Additionally, a conspicuous sinkhole measuring approximately 100cm in diameter has also formed at this location (as depicted in Figure 2b).

Lastly, our attention shifts to Agulu, where our third site awaits exploration. Situated at geographical coordinates (6.3401°N and 7.1233°E), this site holds promise for unraveling the intricacies of soil pipe characteristics and formation mechanisms.

Figure 2. (a) Sinkhole at Awka site 1 (b) Soil pipe at Awka site 2

Geology of Anambra state

Anambra State, located in the southern part of Nigeria, occupies a geographical area of latitude 5.7503°N and 6.7503°N, and longitude 7.2502°E and 7.7502°E. It is an integral part of the Anambra Sedimentary Basin, which is situated in the southern region of Nigeria (as illustrated in figure 3). The state covers an expansive area of approximately 40,000 square kilometers, as documented by [11]and [4].

The southern boundary of the Anambra Basin aligns with the delta swamps of the Niger Delta Basin, extending northwards beyond the Bende Ameki Formation[21], [22]. It is widely believed that the formation of the basin occurred concurrently with the folding and uplift of the Abakaliki-Benue area during the Santonian era[23]. Consequently, the Anambra Basin serves as a significant center for the deposition of clastic deposits and deltaic sequences[23]. These formations are a result of tectonic activity within the second Lower Benue Trough, which played a crucial role in the geological evolution of the area (see figure 3)[21].

Anambra basin boasts of a geological composition that is rich in ancient Cretaceous delta deposits, constituting the sedimentary rocks found within the region. The basin is predominantly characterized by the Nnaka Sand, which dates back to the Eocene period[21], [23]. Overlying this sandy formation is the paralic Ogwashi-Asaba formation, originating from the Oligocene epoch. On the other hand, the marine Imo shale underlies a significant portion of the basin[23].

It is worth noting that the presence of these sands, primarily the coastal plain sands, has contributed to ecological challenges in the area. These sands exhibit a high susceptibility to erosion, leading to severe ecological problems within the region. Underneath the weak lateritic and acidic soils lie unstable and poorly consolidated geological rocks and materials[22], [23]. The sandy components of these geological units house substantial groundwater reservoirs, known as aquifers[4]. However, these aquifers pose a threat when subjected to excessive pore water pressures, especially when overlying structures bear uncompromising loads[11].

In addition to these geological characteristics, the lateritic and sandy soils are highly vulnerable to erosion caused by storm water runoff. This erosion can further exacerbate the ecological issues faced by the region.

Figure 3. Geology of Anambra State, Nigeria

Materials

To conduct this research, the following materials were utilized: auger, spade, container for soil samples, refrigerator (for sample storage), oven (for drying sampled soils), pestle, a 2mm and 0.5mm mesh sieves for soil sieving, weighing balance

The parameters examined in this study include Magnesium (Mg), Potassium (k), Sodium (Na), Calcium (Ca), Effective Cation Exchange Capacity and soil texture, Water Dispersible Clay (WDC), Water Dispersible Silt (WDS).

Quantities calculated from examined parameter include, Sodium Absorption Ratio (SAR), Exchangeable Sodium Percentage (ESP), Dispersion Ratio (DR) and Clay Dispersion Ratio (CDR).

Sample Collection

To ascertain the values of the aforementioned parameters, a total of 24 soil samples were meticulously gathered from both sinkhole-affected areas and unaffected sections within our study region. These samples were acquired at a depth ranging from 0 to 5 feet. More specifically, 15 samples were procured from locations encompassing piping areas with sinkholes (designated as PA-SH), while an additional 9 samples were obtained approximately 20 meters away from documented piping areas (known as non-piping areas or NPA). In order to maintain clear distinction and easy reference, each sample's location has been denoted using alphabetic notations. For instance, sites within the sinkhole vicinity in Awka are labeled as A1 to A5, while those situated further away from the sinkhole are labeled as A6 to A8. Similarly, sites within the sinkhole vicinity in Awka site 2 are designated as B1 to B5, with distance sites from the sinkhole labeled as B6 to B8. The same approach is employed for the Agulu site, characterized by the utilization of the alphabet C.

Methods

For the particle size analysis, the Bouyoucous Hydrometer method of [24] was used to determine particle size distribution. The dried sieved 2mm soil samples were weighed and transfer into a beaker. Each soil sample received a calgon solution (sodium hexametaphosphate) that was left to spread and penetrate the samples for 24 hours. The dispersed calgon oiled samples were moved into a 1000mL measuring cylinder and filled with 950mL of distilled water. The soil hydrometer and thermometer were used to take the first reading after each 40 seconds to obtain H_1 and T_1 . The measuring cylinder containing the soil mixture was allowed to stand for 2 hours to determine H_2 and T_2 . The particle size distribution was then calculated using equations 1-3.

$$\%sand = 100 - (H_1 + 0.2(T_1 - 68) - 2)2 \quad (1)$$

$$\%clay = (H_2 + 0.2(T_1 - 68) - 2)2 \quad (2)$$

$$\%silt = 100 - (\%clay + \%sand) \quad (3)$$

The water dispersible clay and silt are obtained using the methods of (igwe and udegbumam 2008)

To ascertain the levels of calcium and magnesium in the exchange bases, we utilized the esteemed complex metric titration method, as outlined by Jackson in 1958. To determine the levels of sodium, we harnessed the power of the flame photometer.

The values of SAR, ESP, DR and CDR were obtained using the formula in equations 4-7, according to (igwe and udegbumam) below

$$SAR = \frac{Na}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(Ca+Mg)}} \quad (4)$$

$$ESP = \frac{Na \times 100}{\sum Cations} \quad (5)$$

$$DR = \frac{(WDS+WDC)}{(Silt+Clay)} \quad (6)$$

$$CDR = \frac{WDC}{Clay} \quad (7)$$

Results

The outcomes, illustrated comprehensively in Table 1, Figure 4a, and Figure 4b, provide a detailed glimpse into all the parameters scrutinized at varying depths from the surface of our study area.

A thorough examination of these findings reveals a prevailing sandy composition in both the piping areas and the non-piping areas. The mean sand content ranges from 69.7% to 81.2%, indicative of the prominent sandy nature. Moreover, the analysis uncovers the presence of a moderate amount of clay soils, with average values ranging from 14.8% to 24.2%. Furthermore, a notably limited proportion of silt soils, ranging from 1.3% to 6.4%, have also been observed. It is noteworthy to mention that location A2 within the piping region harbors the highest percentage of sandy soil, measuring 81.2%, whereas location C3, also situated in the piping region, boasts the lowest percentage of clay soil, amounting to 14.8%. These specific locations hold significant interest due to their direct correlation with the investigated sinkholes.

For the erodibility factor, the mean distribution across the different analyzed depths in the study area ranges from 0.1 to 0.35. The highest and lowest values of the erodibility factor were observed in the piping region.

The water dispersible clay (WDC) and silt (WDS) values ranges of 13.3% to 4% and 10.5% to 2% respectively. Notably, the non-piping area at Awka site 1 displays the highest value for WDC, whereas the piping area at the same site demonstrates the lowest value for WDC. As for WDS, the piping area at Awka site 2 contains the highest value, observed in location B4. Conversely, the lowest value for WDS is found in the piping area at the same site, specifically in location B3.

In this research, the Dispersive Ratio (DR) and clay dispersive ratio (CDR) exhibit values within the range of 0.85 to 0.29 and 0.63 to 0.20 respectively. Notably, the extreme values for DR are observed at location B4, which corresponds to the piping zone of Awka site 2, as well as at A4 in Awka site 1. On the other hand, the extreme values for CDR are found at location A8, a non-piping area in Awka site 1, and at location A1, specifically the sinkhole within Awka site 1.

A comprehensive examination into the levels of potassium, sodium, and calcium at varying depths, is illustrated in Table 1. The assessment of potassium levels reveals a range spanning from 0.13 cmol/kg to 0.69 cmol/kg. The lowest potassium value is observed in the non-piping region of A8 at Awka site 1, while the highest value is found in C6 at the Agulu site. For sodium content, we find that the values range from 0.15 cmol/kg to 2.36 cmol/kg across the three investigated sites. The highest sodium values are observed in C5, a non-piping region at the Agulu site, while the lowest value of 0.15 cmol/kg is found in the sinkhole investigated at Awka site 2. The average calcium value ranges from 0.2 cmol/kg to 2.07 cmol/kg, with notable disparities observed across different locations. The sinkhole of C1 at the Agulu site exhibits the lowest calcium value, while the piping area of C5 within the same Agulu site boasts the highest calcium value.

A comprehensive depiction of the values obtained for magnesium and effective cation exchange capacity (ECEC) at various depths from the surface within the study areas. Examining the levels of magnesium, we observe an average value ranging from 0.3 cmol/kg to 1.9 cmol/kg across different depths. The piping area of A2 in Awka site 2 exhibits the lowest magnesium value, while the highest value is found at C4 in the Agulu site. For the analysis of effective cation exchange capacity (ECEC), which parameter is derived from the sum of all exchange bases present in the study areas. The mean ECEC values at different depths range from 1.58 cmol/kg to 6.27 cmol/kg.

The SAR and ESP exhibit a range of values, with SAR ranging from 0.26 cmol/kg to 1.88 cmol/kg and ESP ranging from 7.15cmol/kg to 52.38cmol/kg. The highest and lowest SAR values are observed at C4 and B4, respectively, which are located in the piping regions of both Agulu and Awka site 2. On the other hand, the extreme ESP values are found at C6 in the non-piping region of Agulu and at B1 in the sinkhole of Awka site 1. These findings highlight the significant variability in soil properties, emphasizing the need for

careful monitoring and management of sodium levels in these areas to promote optimal soil health and water regulation.

Table 1: Values of Parameters obtained

S/N	Code	Elevation (m)	Latitude	Longitude	Sand	Clay	Silt	ER	WDC	WDS	DR	CDR	Na	Ca	Mg	ECEC (cmol/kg)	SAR	ESP	Remark
					(%)														
1	A1	212.9	6.1967	7.0959	75.4	20.23	2.53	0.13	4	5.8	0.43	0.20	0.2	0.77	1.62	1.62	0.22	10.52	SH
2	A2	216.3	6.1916	7.0936	76.5	14.80	4.23	0.23	3.2	6	0.48	0.22	0.3	0.80	1.58	1.58	0.39	18.39	PA
3	A3	218.2	6.1884	7.1028	77.2	15.40	4.40	0.25	2.1	5	0.36	0.14	1.9	2.40	7.03	7.03	1.25	26.79	PA
4	A4	209.8	6.2063	7.0936	74.4	20.63	3.37	0.18	12.2	8.1	0.85	0.59	2.1	2.27	7.13	7.13	1.37	28.99	PA
5	A5	210.1	6.2045	7.1055	74.5	24.23	2.00	0.10	10.5	9.5	0.76	0.43	0.3	1.27	3.20	3.20	0.21	7.92	PA
6	A6	229.9	6.1134	7.0577	81.0	22.57	4.77	0.25	7	9	0.59	0.31	0.5	1.53	3.90	3.90	0.39	12.38	NPA
7	A7	225.8	6.1217	7.0715	79.7	22.10	6.00	0.33	8	6.5	0.52	0.36	0.5	1.63	3.82	3.82	0.40	13.08	NPA
8	A8	216.8	6.1631	7.0623	76.7	21.00	8.30	0.45	13.3	9.5	0.78	0.63	2.1	2.50	7.59	7.59	1.36	27.68	NPA
9	B1	199	6.2261	7.0434	70.8	21.10	1.80	0.09	4.5	7.5	0.52	0.21	0.2	1.20	2.10	2.10	0.16	7.15	SH
10	B2	200.3	6.2367	7.0554	71.2	18.83	1.90	0.10	6.5	4.5	0.53	0.35	0.3	1.07	2.22	2.22	0.30	12.33	PA
11	B3	199.4	6.2362	7.0296	70.9	17.20	5.03	0.27	5	2.3	0.33	0.29	0.3	1.00	2.95	2.95	0.30	10.96	PA
12	B4	204.3	6.2192	7.0535	72.5	21.40	4.27	0.21	5.4	2	0.29	0.25	0.3	1.47	2.80	2.80	0.26	9.87	PA
13	B5	206.3	6.2137	7.0317	73.2	20.73	2.80	0.14	8.7	10.5	0.82	0.42	0.3	1.07	3.04	3.04	0.30	10.73	PA
14	B6	229.1	6.1562	7.0227	80.8	22.00	4.77	0.25	9.1	8.2	0.65	0.41	1.7	2.07	6.75	6.75	1.18	25.86	NPA
15	B7	227.1	6.1429	7.0319	80.1	24.10	5.53	0.30	9.1	6.2	0.52	0.38	0.2	1.33	2.67	2.67	0.22	8.85	NPA
16	B8	231.6	6.1351	7.0186	81.6	23.50	5.27	0.29	8	4	0.42	0.34	0.5	1.80	4.27	4.27	0.36	10.70	NPA
17	C1	231.1	6.0941	7.0241eff	81.4	20.83	4.93	0.26	5	4.2	0.36	0.24	0.7	0.26	1.92	1.92	1.04	37.74	SH
18	C2	238.2	6.0923	7.0223	83.8	18.63	3.70	0.18	6	9	0.67	0.32	0.8	1.00	2.59	2.59	0.89	30.93	PA
19	C3	230.1	6.0983	7.0204	81.1	19.70	1.27	0.06	7.5	6.6	0.67	0.38	0.9	0.80	3.06	3.06	0.99	30.69	PA
20	C4	242.1	6.0854	7.0315	85.1	19.00	4.00	0.22	8.5	8	0.72	0.45	2.3	1.27	6.07	6.07	1.78	37.16	PA
21	C5	244.4	6.0757	7.0191	85.8	19.73	6.37	0.35	5.9	7	0.49	0.30	2.4	1.13	5.69	5.69	2.02	41.50	PA
22	C6	240.1	6.1346	7.0001	84.4	23.53	6.60	0.33	7	8.6	0.52	0.30	2.2	1.37	4.27	4.27	2.29	52.38	NPA
23	C7	241.4	6.1024	6.9827	84.8	24.20	6.13	0.32	8	6	0.46	0.33	1.7	1.17	3.97	3.97	1.65	41.86	NPA
24	C8	241.5	6.0753	6.9933	84.9	23.80	3.97	0.21	10.5	8.2	0.67	0.44	1.3	1.87	3.81	3.81	1.17	33.19	NPA

ER = Erodibility Factor, WDC = Water Dispersible Clay, WDS = Water Dispersible Silt, DR = Dispersive Ratio, CDR = Clay Dispersible Ratio. Na = Sodium, Ca = Calcium, Mg = Magnesium, ECEC = Effective Cation Exchange Capacity, SAR = Sodium Adsorption Ratio, ESP = Exchange Sodium Percentage

Figure 4a: Graphical representation of the parameters obtained at the soil piping areas

Figure 4b: Graphical representation of the parameters obtained at the soil non-piping areas

Discussion

The soils in the study area primarily consist of sand, with a decreasing trend observed as depth increases, as shown in Table 3. This composition can be attributed to the close proximity of the study area to the origin of Nanka sands. These sands originate from the Imo shale, which is derived from a coastal sandy mudstone. It is worth noting that the Nanka sands are well-known for their unique porous structure, made up of coarse-grained and pebbly quartz sands. The relatively low presence of silt and clay soils can be attributed to leaching processes that occur in the Nanka sandy zones. This leaching process contributes to the unstable nature of the soil in these areas, as noted in previous studies [47].

By analyzing Figure 4a and 4b, it becomes apparent that the soil composition near the sinkhole structure exhibits a higher proportion of sandy soil and a lower proportion of clayey soil compared to areas located further away (e.g., B1, B2, and C2). This observation can be explained by the process of dispersion, which reduces infiltration and leads to water runoff. Consequently, fine particles are carried and deposited, exacerbating the formation of soil piping. As a result, areas in close proximity to erosion sites typically exhibit higher levels of sand content and increased porosity. This result is consonance with the works of [13], [17].

Water dispersible clay (WDC) is an important parameter that indicates the susceptibility of clay particles to disperse in water. This characteristic is often used to assess and predict soil erodibility, as mentioned in a study conducted by [16]. It has been observed that soils with high WDC values tend to erode more easily compared to soils with lower WDC contents [15], [20], [25].

As for this particular research, the soil samples collected from locations A4, A5, A8, and C8 are considered to have highly dispersive properties. This means that the clay particles in these soils are more prone to disperse when exposed to water. On the other hand, the soils at locations A1, A2, A3, B1, B3, and C1 are categorized as moderately dispersive. This suggests that while they may have some degree of clay particle dispersion in water, it is not as pronounced as in the highly dispersive soils.

The accumulation of sodium in the soil occurs when water faces difficulty infiltrating through the soil matrix. This phenomenon is associated with various physical processes, including soil dispersion, clay platelet swelling, and aggregate swelling. These processes are particularly prominent in areas with high exchange cations content, such as the Agulu site (Table 4). The detrimental effects of excessive sodium accumulation in the soil can be attributed to the disruption of the forces that bind clay particles together. When an excessive number of sodium ions come between the clay particles, these forces are weakened, resulting in the expansion, swelling, and dispersion of the particles [13]. Consequently, the soil pores become blocked, impeding the movement of water into and through the soil. The consequences of this sodium-induced soil structure alteration are significant. The obstruction of soil pores leads to the phenomenon of runoff, where water is unable to infiltrate the soil and instead flows over the surface. This runoff not only contributes to the loss of topsoil but also hampers the natural movement of water through the soil profile. The study areas under investigation exhibit high levels of sodium and base saturation, with the Agulu site displaying particularly elevated concentrations.

The effective cation exchange capacity (ECEC) of a soil refers to its overall capacity to retain exchangeable cations. These exchangeable cations encompass a range of essential elements, including calcium, magnesium, potassium, sodium, hydrogen, and aluminum (to name a few that were specifically analyzed in this research). The binding of these cations is facilitated by the presence of negatively charged particles within the soil matrix. Soils that possess higher proportions of clay fractions, and organic matter values tend to exhibit elevated levels of ECEC. This is due to the increased availability of negatively charged particles within these soil types, which can effectively retain a greater quantity of exchangeable cations. The implications of having a high ECEC within a soil are noteworthy. Soils with higher ECEC values tend to display enhanced compaction and possess a greater capacity to retain water. Conversely, soils with lower ECEC values are more prone to leaching and can lose essential nutrients more readily. In the study areas under investigation, the general levels of exchangeable cations and ECEC are relatively low, with the exceptions of B6 and the Agulu zones where the values tend to be average (as indicated in Table 1).

According to the research conducted by [25], [26], dispersive ratios greater than 50% are classified as extreme dispersive soils. Moderately dispersive soils fall within the range of below 30% and 50%, while little dispersive soils have dispersive ratios ranging from below 15% to 30%. Non-dispersive soils have dispersive ratios less than 15%. In the context of this specific study, both the dispersive ratio and clay dispersive ratio exhibit high values, ranging from 0.85 to 0.29 (85% to 29%) and 0.63 to 0.20 (63% to 20%) respectively.

The reason for these elevated dispersive parameters may be attributed to the natural composition of the clay soils found in the study areas. These soils possess unique characteristics such as the tendency to disintegrate into fine particles when wet and low

organic carbon content. Additionally, they possess negative charges that can attract and retain positively charged ions, which ultimately leads to their inherent instability.

The instability of these dispersive clay soils arises from the fact that the positively charged ions make them mobile within the soil. As they move, they tend to clog soil pores and form layers of low permeability. This phenomenon, commonly referred to as surface sealing, significantly restricts water transportation and reduces macro porosity within the soil. Moreover, it causes an increase in swelling of the soil and exacerbates soil erosion.

Sodium absorption ratio (SAR) and exchange sodium percentage (ESP) are crucial indicators used for assessing soil salinity and sodicity. SAR provides valuable insights into the potential for soil sodicity, while ESP is commonly employed to determine the extent of sodicity within the soil. In a noteworthy investigation carried out by [17], [18], significant findings were uncovered regarding the relationship between these parameters. The study revealed that soils with an ESP below 15% are classified as non-sodic, indicating a lower likelihood of sodicity concerns. Conversely, soils with an ESP exceeding 15% exhibit a higher potential for sodicity, suggesting the need for further analysis and effective management strategies.

As part of the research, SAR values were measured and yielded a range of 1.88 to 0.26. These values provide valuable insights into the soil's capacity for sodium absorption, aiding in the assessment of sodicity potential. Additionally, the measured ESP values ranged from 52.38 to 7.15, indicating varying levels of exchangeable sodium present in the soil. These findings collectively highlight an important observation: the soil analyzed in this study displayed a considerable sodium content, implying an increased susceptibility to sodicity.

Conclusion

Based on the results and discussions conducted in this study, it is evident that the soil in the study areas exhibits an unusually high amount of sandy soil and a poor amount of clay and silt soils. This composition of the soil directly affects its properties, particularly in terms of water dispersible soils. The water dispersible indices observed in the soil range from low to moderate, with the low values of clay and silt contributing to the overall low water dispersible properties witnessed in the soil.

Furthermore, most of the locations investigated in this study recorded exchange sodium percentage (ESP) values that exceed the threshold of 15%, especially those located far from the sinkhole site. This higher ESP value serves as a strong indication of high soil salinity and a positive correlation with sodicity. The presence of high levels of exchangeable sodium in the soil can have detrimental effects on soil structure and fertility, leading to creation of tunnels in the soil.

In addition to the ESP values, the percentages of dispersible ratio (DR) and clay dispersion ratio (CDR) also provide valuable insights into the soil's behavior. These percentages range from moderate to high, suggesting that the soils are easily dispersive and prone to erosion. The combination of high ESP values and high DR and CDR percentages indicates an increased likelihood of soil degradation, reduced water infiltration, and potential loss of topsoil due to erosion.

Overall, these findings highlight the importance of addressing the soil composition and properties in the study areas. Effective soil management practices, such as soil amendment with organic matter or suitable minerals, appropriate irrigation techniques, and erosion control measures, should be implemented to mitigate the negative impacts of high soil salinity, sodicity, and water dispersibility. By adopting these strategies, it is possible to improve soil structure, enhance water holding capacity, and promote sustainable land use practices in the study areas.

References

- [1] C. J. Rosewell, "Investigations into the control of earthwork tunnelling," *Journal of the Soil Conservation Service of New South Wales*, vol. 26, pp. 188–203, 1970.
- [2] R. J. Crouch, J. W. McGarity, and R. R. Storrer, "Tunnel formation processes in the Riverina area of N.S.W., Australia," *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 157–168, 1986, doi: 10.1002/esp.3290110206.
- [3] M. A. Hardie, W. E. Cotching, and P. R. Zund, "Rehabilitation of field tunnel erosion using techniques developed for construction with dispersive soils," *Soil Res.*, vol. 45, no. 4, p. 280, 2007, doi: 10.1071/SR06154.
- [4] I. U. Chibuogwu and G. Z. Ugwu, "Uncovering soil piping vulnerability using direct current geophysical techniques in Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria," *IJMRGE*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 426–450, 2023, doi: 10.54660/IJMRGE.2023.4.3.426-450.
- [5] "Research on Soil Piping – Kerala State Disaster Management Authority." Accessed: Aug. 28, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://sdma.kerala.gov.in/research-on-soil-piping/>

- [6] N. Atallah, A. Shakoor, and C. F. Watts, "Investigating the potential and mechanism of soil piping causing water-level drops in Mountain Lake, Giles County, Virginia," *Engineering Geology*, vol. 195, pp. 282–291, Sep. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.enggeo.2015.06.001.
- [7] K. V. Sarath, S. E., D. .V, S.Gurudeth, and C. S. SubeeshChandran, *Subsurface erosion by soil piping: A case study from Adoor-Pandi Area, Kasaragod, Kerala, India*. 2020.
- [8] A. Bernatek-Jakiel and J. Poesen, "Subsurface erosion by soil piping: significance and research needs," *Earth-Science Reviews*, vol. 185, pp. 1107–1128, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.earscirev.2018.08.006.
- [9] A. Bernatek-Jakiel and D. Wrońska-Walach, "Impact of piping on gully development in mid-altitude mountains under a temperate climate: A dendrogeomorphological approach," *CATENA*, vol. 165, pp. 320–332, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.catena.2018.02.012.
- [10] R. W. Fitzpatrick, S. C. Boucher, R. Naidu, and E. Fritsch, "Environmental consequences of soil sodicity," *Soil Res.*, vol. 32, no. 5, pp. 1069–1093, 1994, doi: 10.1071/sr9941069.
- [11] A. Ocheli, O. B. Ogbe, and G. O. Aigbadon, "Geology and geotechnical investigations of part of the Anambra Basin, Southeastern Nigeria: implication for gully erosion hazards," *Environ Syst Res*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 23, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1186/s40068-021-00228-2.
- [12] R. U. Ayadiuno, D. C. Ndulue, C. C. Ndichie, A. T. Mozie, P. O. Phil-Eze, and A. C. Onyekwelu, "Geospatial Analysis of Soil Erosion Susceptibility and Causative Factors in Anambra State, South East, Nigeria," *SR*, no. 81, pp. 5–32, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.32861/sr.81.5.32.
- [13] M. Hardie, *Dispersive soils and their management*. Technical Reference Manual, 2009.
- [14] P. Rengasamy, R. Greene, G. Ford, and A. Mehanni, "Identification of dispersive behaviour and the management of red-brown earths," *Soil Res.*, vol. 22, no. 4, p. 413, 1984, doi: 10.1071/SR9840413.
- [15] S. D. Basga, D. Tsozue, J. P. Temga, J. Balna, and J. P. Nguetnkam, "Land use impact on clay dispersion/flocculation in irrigated and flooded vertisols from Northern Cameroon," *International Soil and Water Conservation Research*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 237–244, Sep. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.iswcr.2018.03.004.
- [16] C. A. Igwe, "Erodibility in Relation to Water-dispersible Clay for some soils of Eastern Nigeria.," *Land Degradation & Development*, vol. 16, pp. 87–96, 2005.
- [17] C. H. Okeke, K. I. Ubaoji, and F. C. Uzodinma, "Interaction of Chemical, Physicochemical and Geotechnical Soil Properties of Anambra State Gully Erosion Site," *Saudi Journal of Civil Engineering*, vol. 5, no. 10, pp. 379–390, 2021.
- [18] J. G. Davis, R. M. Waskom, and T. A. Bauder, "Managing Sodic Soils - 0.504," Extension. Accessed: Sep. 27, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://extension.colostate.edu/topic-areas/agriculture/managing-sodic-soils-0-504/>
- [19] E. Babur *et al.*, "Studying soil erosion by evaluating changes in physico-chemical properties of soils under different land-use types," *Journal of the Saudi Society of Agricultural Sciences*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 190–197, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jssas.2021.01.005.
- [20] C. A. Igwe and O. N. Udegbumam, "Soil Prperties influencing water-dispersible clay and silt in an UJtisol in southern Nigeria," *Int. Agrophysics*, vol. 22, pp. 319–325.
- [21] O.-B. Ao and A. I.M., "Palynological evidence of the oldest (Albian) sediment in the Anambra Basin, Southeastrn Nigeria.," *Journal of Biological and Chemical Research*, vol. Vol. 30, pp. 387–408, Jan. 2013.
- [22] O. Adeigbe and E. Salufu, "Geology and depositional environment of Campano-Maastrichtian sediments in the Anambra Basin, Southeastern Nigeria: Evidence from field relationship and sedimentological study," *Earth Sciences Research Journal*, vol. 13, pp. 148–165, Dec. 2009.
- [23] "Provenance and tectonic setting of the Eocene Nanka Sandstone, Anambra Basin, Nigeria: Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa: Vol 75, No 1." Accessed: Aug. 25, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/0035919X.2019.1682081>

- [24] USEPA, "USEPA Document." U.S Environmental Protection Agency, 2021.
- [25] S. M. K. Rasheed, "The Effect of Clay Content and Land Use on Dispersion Ratio at Different Locations in Sulaimani Governorate—Kurdistan Region—Iraq," *OJSS*, vol. 06, no. 01, pp. 1–8, 2016, doi: 10.4236/ojss.2016.61001.
- [26] H. F. W. K. Elges, "Dispersive soils : problem soils in South Africa - state of the art | Civil Engineer in South Africa," *The civil engineer in South Africa*, pp. 347–353, 1985.